

A Theory of Social Machines

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The emerging concept of Social Machines offers a lens to understand scalable organisation sustained by social interaction through network technologies. Social Machines have avoided mathematical formalism, in part because approaches must jointly consider the humans and the digital tools and substrates that mediate their sociality; and because social phenomena are non-deterministic and emergent.

The underlying basis for the formalism presented in this thesis is informed by Whitehead's Philosophy of Organism. An approach is developed to analyse salient phenomena, including those associated with shared human experience, into coherently changing strands of recurrent activities identifiable across scales of social interaction. Alongside this, a collection of behaviours is proposed as sufficient for a medium to form structures both hosting and coalescing around such processes. Examples of these behaviours are identified in online communities; and the basis is shown capable of representing accepted models of shared engagement, and a well-studied scenario in which emergent organisation produced scientific knowledge.

The basis is mathematically represented in such a way that modelled scenarios can be mapped to stochastic Petri-nets. This representation is applicable across scales, with closed form analysis and model execution showing that small collections and aggregates of these strands may be structurally congruent with individual strands. It is used to construct an accepted model of cultural dissemination and some scenarios that are also described by an existing form of actor network theory extended to support heterogeneous parts.

This foundation is used to develop and represent a formal computational model of Social Machines. The result extends existing concepts by making Social Machines social themselves and by delineating them by their ability to support internal shared intentionality. They overlap by sharing experiences to form ecosystems that support their coalescence and division; while the basis prevents their absolute containment by one another, and supports greater mobility within a population than is generally considered. The theory is proposed to be applicable for doing Web Science; and more broadly, for understanding and constructing systems of concurrently operating components, human or otherwise, that form shared perceptions and structure as part of operating together.

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